

ROLE OF PARENTS IN CHILD EDUCATION

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***Abstract.** This article deals with family relationships, including parenting mistakes and shortcomings in raising a child, as well as how to raise a child are discussed.*

***Keywords:** Family, parents, child, family environment, upbringing, manners, morals, worldview.*

Righteous people have paid great attention to the education of children since ancient times. Because the development or poverty of the nation depends on the education of the youth. It is known from the history of the development of the society that the maturity of the child's personality is formed in the family. The family is a small part of the life of the society, and it is a very important center of education, which is responsible for bringing up a healthy and mature generation. If we call all the members of the Uzbek family literate and educated, we will not be mistaken, under the influence of these opportunities, our sons and daughters are educated, thoughtful, resourceful, business-minded, and intelligent. lib is coming of age.

Child education in the family is of two-fold importance, parents should not be limited to teaching children morals, mental and spiritual knowledge, but they themselves should learn the unique secrets and characteristics of education, its content and essence. they need to be aware of the latest information about its meaning. Parents who have been able to raise their children wisely will spend their lives in comfort and leisure, they will always see nobility, kindness and goodness in their children, their hearts will never feel the pain of injury, they will not feel regret. This is indicated by the proverb of the Uzbek people: "If the wedding grows, the horse will stop (that is, the horse will be saved from riding).»

In our holy religion, parents are responsible for the education of children, and to be more precise, it is the responsibility of the father to support the family financially, and the education of the children is mainly the duty of the father. It is emphasized in the Sharifs. A lot of information can be given about child rearing. Therefore, in this wonderful article, it is necessary to emphasize who is responsible for raising children and to mention some considerations in this regard.

According to the researches of scientists, children who have received mother's upbringing, feel her care and compassion at every step, devote themselves completely to public works, grow up to be healthy, intelligent, well-educated and cheerful it is.

The important tasks of a mother in raising a child are to show kindness to her children, to protect them from various harms, to feed them on time, to wash them, to dress them cleanly, not to let them catch a cold, to be alert and aware, not to be lazy to take care of them. . Every action of a mother in the family circle, every word that comes out of her mouth can have a positive or negative effect on her child's education and formation. Copying her every move, she takes a model of her mother's vocabulary for her unformed vocabulary.

First of all, family peace and kindness of family members to each other occupy an important and worthy place in child upbringing. The nature and behavior of the child depends on the environment in the family. Of course, good children do not grow up on their own, but grow up in the family under the supervision of their parents. Some recommendations have been given by our elders to raise the child to a perfect adult in all respects. It consists of recommendations such as Islam, science, religion, contentment, discipline, conscience and patriotism, justice, chastity,

patience and correctness, and plays an important role in the formation of young people as owners of morals.

A child with a strong imagination receives his first upbringing in the family. The famous Uzbek pedagogue Abdulla Avloni in his work "Turkish Gulistan or Morality" said the following lessons about the first lessons of child education: "It is necessary to start education from the day of birth, to strengthen our body, to clarify our mind"

It is desirable to build the authority of adults in the family not on the basis of intimidation, but on the basis of sincerity and mutual respect. Family members' friendliness, mutual harmony, dressing culture, work activities, conversations about other people and their other qualities bring new symbols to the child's imagination.

Family education plays an important role in the development of a child in the future, the child first sees the image of society in the family, the rights and duties, worldview and moral views of the future citizen are formed in the family, and on this basis, he matures physically and spiritually. For a child, a healthy social-spiritual environment in the family is a source of cultural-spiritual and moral values, traditions, social-life experiences, skills and qualifications. It is refined in the process of family education, the essence of education is to prepare a person for life, and the content, direction, purpose and function of education depend on the social relations of people. Based on these relationships, a person looks at life in a certain way, understands the world through his thinking and forms his attitude towards it, is educated in the spirit of certain moral criteria, because family education, compared to social education, deeply affects the spiritual world, emotions and feelings of children affects.

The spiritual and spiritual environment in the family is of great importance in the upbringing of the child, and the lifestyle of the family members in many cases determines the mental mood, imagination and emotions of the children. So, the family is responsible for the society in bringing up a healthy, well-rounded person.

Every person brought up in a family should embody the universal moral, scientific, religious and other qualities that have reached perfection in themselves, and a person who strives for perfection gradually begins to recognize the world and his identity.

Perfection means that a person is fair, strives for truth and goodness, has good conscience, realizes his mistakes and tries to get rid of them. wakes up from bliss, makes all good wishes come true. It depends on the family and parents to bring up the young generation as a mature, healthy person who can feel the sense of the Motherland.

In order to instill confidence in the future in the young generation, it is appropriate to deeply teach the spiritual and moral heritage of our ancestors, to direct their talents and abilities towards great goals. In short, raising a child in a family is one of the most sensitive issues, because if we consider the child as a seedling, the parents become gardeners. How we take care of the sprout, it will give us such fruit after days, months and years. It is clear from this that it is necessary for parents to be well-educated, knowledgeable, intelligent and aware of modern technologies and to be able to teach them to their children, that is, for this, pedagogical skills are also required from parents.

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